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Evaluation of Typhoid and Malaria Cases as Co-Infections among Students of College of Health Sciences and Technology, Ijero-Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Certain mosquito species can transmit the deadly disease malaria to humans. Salmonella enterica serovar Typhi is the bacteria that cause typhoid fever, an acute systemic illness. Tropical nations are home to the majority of them. They are mostly found in tropical countries. The aim of the study is to determine the coexisting prevalence of typhoid fever and malaria fever infection among students of the College of Health Sciences and Technology, Ijero-Ekiti. . Retrospective study of research design was adopted for this study. All patients attending college of health sciences and technology Ijero-Ekiti health center. Data were collected were meticulously extracted from the hospital's laboratory records from health center of College of Health Sciences and Technology Ijero-Ekiti after permission had been taking from management of health center. SPSS 21.0 was used to analysis the data. The data would be expressed in frequency distribution, percentage and student t-test. Findings of the study were: that 6(14.0%) of the patients were positive for widai test for typhoid fever and 37 (86.0%) were negative.. Age group of the patients tested for typhoid fever: 17-23 years had 44.2%, 22-28 years had 44.2% and 27-31 years had 11.6%. Gender of the patients tested for typhoid fever: male had 20.9% and female had 79.1%.. The infected male with typhoid fever parasite was (2.32%) while uninfected male were 8 (18.60%). Infected female were 5 (11.63%) while uninfected female were 29 (67.44%). Age group of the people undergo malaria test: 17-21 years had 49 (50.0%), 22-28 years had 39 (39.8%) and 27-31`years had 10.2%. Gender of patients did malaria test: male had 12(12.2%) and female had 87.8%. 52 (53.1%) of suspected malaria parasite were positive while 46 (46.9%) were negative. And P. value (0.i05) > Apha value (0.05). This implies that there was no significant different between malaria test results and Wida test results for typhoid fever; therefore, the hypothesis is not rejected. We concluded that the prevalence of typhoid fever is 14.0%, prevalence of malaria fever is 53.15%. And there are no difference between prevalence of typhoid fever and malaria fever. We recommended that people should go for malaria test and typhoid fever test simultaneously because of co- existing infections

Key Words: Infection, Fever, life-threatening, morbidity and mortality

Introduction

Typhoid fever and malaria are two common infectious illnesses that have a significant impact on public health in underdeveloped countries like Nigeria (Olowolafe et al., 2024). Malaria is caused by a parasite called Plasmodium. When humans are bitten by an infected mosquito, they get infected with the parasite. Malaria patients typically have a high fever and shivering chills. Malaria is a dangerous illness that people can contract from certain types of mosquitoes. Tropical nations are typically home to it. It can be prevented and treated. The symptoms might be mild or perhaps lethal. Mild symptoms include fever, chills, and headache. Severe symptoms include fatigue, confusion, difficulty breathing, and seizures. Travelers, newborns, children under five, pregnant women and girls, and those with HIV or AIDS are at higher risk of developing a serious infection. (WHO, November 2024). After being bitten by an infected mosquito, symptoms often appear 10 to 15 days later. Some people may experience modest symptoms, particularly those who have already experienced malaria. Early testing is crucial since certain symptoms of malaria are not distinct. Extreme exhaustion and lethargy, impaired awareness, repeated convulsions, breathing difficulties, black or bloody urine, jaundice (yellowing of the skin and eyes), and abnormal bleeding are examples of serious symptoms (WHO, Nov. 2024).

Transmission cycle of malaria

(Mayo Clinic Staff, 2023).

According to WHO estimates, there were around 228 million cases of malaria and 405,000 fatalities from the disease in 2018, with 93.8% of those deaths occurring in sub-Saharan Africa. The most lethal of the four human malaria parasites, *Plasmodium falciparum* species, is responsible for most infections (Francky et al., 2023). Malaria continues to be a crippling problem, causing over 600,000 deaths annually and impeding socioeconomic advancement in endemic areas, despite persistent mitigation efforts that include vector control, timely diagnosis, and effective treatments (WHO, 2020).

The most dangerous of them is typhoid, which is mostly caused by *Salmonella enterica* serotype typhi and, to a lesser degree, *S. enterica* serotypes paratyphi A, B, and C. It can manifest in many different ways, from simple instances of diarrhea with low-grade fever to an overwhelming septic infection. Fever, malaise, widespread stomach discomfort, and constipation are the typical symptoms. Within a month of starting, untreated typhoid fever can develop into delirium, obtundation, intestinal bleeding, bowel perforation, and even death. According to Kakaria et al. (2014), survivors may experience long-term or irreversible mental issues.

The *S. Typhi* bacteria causes typhoid fever. It results in diarrhea, flu-like symptoms, and a high temperature. Even if a person is not ill, they can still spread typhoid. Typhoid should be treated with medicines

as soon as possible since it might be fatal. if individuals visit or reside in a region where typhoid is prevalent. In poor nations, typhoid fever is more prevalent in rural regions with inadequate sanitation. Typhoid mostly affects nations in South and Southeast Asia, Central and South America, Africa, and the Caribbean (WHO, 2023). In tropical and subtropical nations, typhoid fever and malaria continue to be the leading causes of illness and death. Nowadays, it is typical to witness individuals receiving treatment for both illnesses at the same time. These illnesses, which are mostly linked to poverty and underdevelopment and have high rates of morbidity and mortality, are prevalent in many nations with warm, humid climates, unhygienic practices, poverty, and illiteracy. Furthermore, research on the coinfection of typhoid fever and malaria has previously been conducted in Africa, particularly in Nigeria (Sale et al., 2020).

Information on concurrent typhoid and malaria coinfection in Ekiti State, Nigeria, is still sparse in the state's rural communities. This motivated the researcher to evaluate the prevalence of typhoid fever and malaria parasite as coinfections among students of the College of Health Sciences and Technology, Ijero-Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria. The aim of the study is to evaluate prevalence of typhoid fever and malaria parasite as coinfection among students of college of health sciences and technology, Ijero-Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria; to determine different between prevalence of malaria fever and typhoid fever infections among the students college of health sciences and technology, Ijero-Ekiti Ekiti state; to determine the age group of patients infected with malaria and typhoid fever in college of health sciences and technology, Ijero-Ekiti Ekiti state and to determine the gender of patents infected with malaria and typhoid fever in college of health sciences and technology, Ijero-Ekiti Ekiti state.

Method

A retrospective study of research design was adopted for this study. Purposive sampling technique was used to select 89 patients tested for malaria fever and 43 tested for typhoid fever by the WIDA test attending the College of Health Sciences and Technology Ijeo-Ekiti health center from January to June 2024. Permission was obtained from the medical direction of the college health center. Then, relevant data were meticulously extracted from the hospital's laboratory records using a structured Excel spreadsheet. The extracted variables included sex, age, and diagnostic test results for malaria and typhoid cases. SPSS 21.0 was used to analyze the data. The data would be expressed in frequency distribution, percentage and student t-test

Result

Table 1: Sociodemographic characteristics of suspected typhoid fever cases

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	9	20.9	20.9
Female	34	79.1	100.0
Total	43	100.0	
Age group for suspected typhoid fever patients			
17-21 Years	19	44.2	44.2
22-28 Years	19	44.2	88.4
27-31 Years	5	11.6	100.0
Total	43	100.0	

Table 1 above revealed that the males have 20.9% and the females have 79.1%, and 17-23 years have 44.2%, 22-28 years have 44.2% and 27-31 years have 11.6%

Table 2: Wida test result for suspected typhoid fever cases

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
POSITIVE	6	14.0	14.0
NEGATIVE	37	86.0	100.0
Total	43	100.0	

Table 2: revealed that 6(14.0%) of the patients were positive and 37 (86.0%) were negative

Table 3: Gender for suspected typhoid fever cases * WIDA test results for crosstabulation

		WIDA test result		Total
		Positive	Negative	
Gender for	Male	1(2.33%)	8 (18.60%)	9 (20.93%)
	Female	5 (11.63%)	29(67.44%)	34 (79.07)
Total		6 (13.96)	37 (86.4)	43 (100%)

Table 3 revealed that infected male with typhoid fever parasite was 1 (2.32%) while uninfected male were 8 (18.60%). Infected female were 5 (11.63%) while uninfected female were 29 (67.44%)

Table 4: Socio demographic characteristics of suspected malarial fever cases

	Frequency	Percent	Cumulative Percent
Male	12	12.2	12.2
Female	86	87.8	100
Total	98	100	
Age group for suspected typhoid fever patients			
17-21 Years	49	50.0	50.0
22-28 Years	39	39.8	89.8
27-31Years	10	10.2	100.0
Total	89	100.0	

Table 4 above revealed that revealed that male have 12(12.2%) and female have 87.8% and revealed that Age group 17-21 years have 49 (50.0%), 22-28 years have 39 (39.8%) and 27-31`years have 10.2%

Table 5: Age group for suspected Malaria fever patients * Malaria test result Crosstabulation

Count		MALARIA TEST RESULT		Total
		POSITIVE	NEGATIVE	
AGE GROUP FOR M	17-21 YEARS	27(27.55%)	22(22.45%)	49(50 %)
	22-28YEARS	20 (20.41%)	19(19.39%)	39(39.8%)
	27-31YEARS	5(5.1%)	5(5.1%)	10(10.20)
Total		52 (53.06%)	46(46.94%)	98 (100%)

Table 5 revealed that 17-21 years of the suspected malaria fever patients; 27 (27.55%) of them are positive while 22 (22.45%) of them are negative. 22-28 years of the suspected malaria fever patients; 20 (20.41%) of them are positive while 19 (19.39%) of them are negative. And 27-31 years of the suspected malaria fever patients; 5 (5.1%) of them are positive while 5 (5.1%) of them are negative

Table 6 :Gender of malaria parasite suspected cases * Malaria test result crosstabulation

	MALARIA TEST RESULT		Total
	POSITIVE	NEGATIVE	
MALE	7 (7.14%)	5 (5.10%)	12 (12.24%)
FEMALE	45 (45.91%)	41 (41.84%)	86 (87.76%)
Total	52 (53.06%)	46 (46.94%)	98 (100%)

Table 6 revealed that 7 (7.14%) of the male patients tested positive to malaria test, while 5 (5.10%) are negative. 54(45.91%) of the female patients are positive to malaria test, while 41 (41.84%) are negative.

Table 7: T- test analysis Statistics

	MALARIA TEST RESULT	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	dt	t	p
WIDA TEST RESULT FOR TYPHOID FEVER	POSITIVE	22	1.8182	.39477	.08417	41	-.806	0.105
	NEGATIVE	21	1.9048	.30079	.06564	39.11	-.811	

From table 7, the p-value (0.105) > alpha value (0.05). This implies that there was no significant difference between malaria test results and Widal test results for typhoid fever; therefore, the hypothesis is not rejected. Both malaria fever and typhoid fever have equal prevalence

Discussion

The finding of this study revealed that males have 20.9% and females have 79.1%, and 17-23 years have 44.2%, 22-28 years have 44.2%, and 27-31 years have 11.6%. Therefore, there are more than males. The reason for this finding is that more females are admitted to the College of Health Sciences and Technology, Ijero-Ekiti, than males.

The finding of this study revealed that 6 (14.0%) of the patients were positive and 37 (86.0%) were negative. Therefore, the prevalence of typhoid fever is 14.0%. This finding is lower than the study carried out by Ehidihamen et al. (2025), which stated that a systematic review and meta-analysis of studies conducted in Nigeria between 2000 and 2018 reported an overall pooled prevalence of typhoid fever of 20.9%. What makes this study different from Ehidihamen et al., 2025, may be due to the knowledge acquired by the students about the prevention of typhoid fever.

Also, this study revealed that infected males with the typhoid fever parasite were 1 (2.32%), while uninfected males were 8 (18.60%). Infected females were 5 (11.63%), while uninfected females were 29 (67.44%). This finding shows that females are more infected by typhoid fever than males. Table 4 above revealed that males have 12(12.2%) and females have 87.8%, and revealed that age group 17-21 years have 49 (50.0%), 22-28 years have 39 (39.8%) and 27-31`years have 10.2%. Therefore, female are more than male. The reason for this finding may due to fact that female are more admitted to the college of health sciences and technology Ijero-Ekiti than male.

Furthermore, the finding of this study revealed that of the 17-21 years of the suspected malaria fever patients; 27 (27.55%) of them are positive while 22 (22.45%) of them are negative. 22-28 years of the suspected malaria fever patients; 20 (20.41%) of them are positive while 19 (19.39%) of them are negative. And 27-31 years of the suspected malaria fever patients; 5 (5.1%) of them are positive while 5 (5.1%) of them are negative. Age group 17- 21 years have highest prevalence of malaria fever 27 (27.55%). This finding stated that prevalence of malaria fever is 52 (53.06%). This finding is little different to the study reported by Olorunniyi, 2024 stated that

(51.5%) had malaria in 2019 while 604 (48.6%) had malaria in 2021 with no significant difference. This finding is lower than the 60.5% recorded among university students in Akure (Simon-Oke and Akinbote, 2020). The differences in prevalence rates may be influenced by the varying study populations: this study's hospital-based records likely reflect higher prevalence due to individuals seeking medical care, whereas community-based studies may include asymptomatic or mildly symptomatic individuals, potentially resulting in different prevalence rates. The differences prevalence of malaria cases may also due to different years by which the research works were carried out.

Moreover, the finding of this study revealed that 7 (7.14%) of the male patient are positive to malaria test while 5(5.10%) are negative. 54(45.91%) of the female patients are positive to malaria test while 41(41.84%) are negative. This findings is different from the study reported by Olorunniyi, 2024 stated that malaria cases was higher in males than females in both years but without significant difference.

From table 7, the p-value (0.105) > apha value (0.05). This implies that there was no significant different between malaria test results and Widai test results for typhoid fever; therefore, the hypotheses is not rejected. The both malaria fever and typhoid fever have equal prevalence. The finding is different to Olowolafe, et al, 2024 stated that prevalence of malaria and typhoid cases are significant different.

Conclusion

The researcher concluded that there are more malaria and typhoid cases than males. The prevalence of malaria fever and typhoid cases are 53.06% and 14.0% respectively. The both malaria fever and typhoid fever have equal prevalence among the college of health sciences and technology, Ijero-Ekiti.

Recommendation

1. The researcher recommended that since typhoid fever can be caused by poverty, overcrowding and poor hygiene, and efforts should be made to improve on the living conditions of the students of college of health sciences and technology, Ijero-Ekiti.
2. Ministry of Health, Health educators and concern NGOs should intensive campaign against spreading of typhoid and malaria fever as co-infection in Ekiti state.
3. We recommended that people should go for malaria and typhoid fever test simultaneously because of co- existing infection and Federal and state ministry of health and health educators should educate the people about the co-infection of typhoid fever and malaria fever parasite in order to prevent spreading of the infection

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